

Evaluation and analysis of citizens' satisfaction with the quality of life and its impact on urban development (Case study: the city of Khash)

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾ **Shoaib Kahraze**-MSc student in Department of Geography and Urban Planning, College of human science, Zahehan Branch, Islamic Azad University, Zahedan, Iran ⁽²⁾ **Gholam Reza Miri (Corresponding author)**-Assistant professor in Department of Geography and Urban Planning, College of human science, Zahehan Branch, Islamic Azad University, Zahedan, Iran -⁽³⁾ **Morteza Esmael Nezhad**-Assistant professor in Department of Geography, University of Birjand, Birjand, Iran

Abstract

Quality of urban life is one of the most important fields of urban studies in different countries which have multiple components of the social, environmental and economic. Because of its role as an important tool in the management and planning of urban and generally determine the habitable of cities, attention to this index has been increased in cities. The present research follows Evaluation and analysis of citizens' satisfaction with the quality of life and its impact on urban development (The case study: the city of Khash). The research methodology is descriptive-analytic and is based on the library and field investigation as questionnaire. The results of investigations showed that the constituent elements of environmental quality in both studied areas, although with slight differences, are similar. It was also specified that although citizens' satisfaction with the quality of the environment isn't desirable, but new residents are more satisfied than the old residents. Satisfaction survey found that constituent elements of environmental quality are at the local level. In the new fabric of the city, the greatest impact on citizens' satisfaction was related to socioeconomic dimension and the citizens of the old fabric of the city have the greatest satisfaction from the perceived dimension.

Key words: Satisfaction, quality of life, new and old urban fabric, Khash

Introduction

Urban areas are centers of economic, social and political growth in every country that have demonstrated themselves as the most attractive places to build wealth, work, creativity and innovation, However, some urban areas are facing with significant challenges in the areas of physical and environmental degradation, social exclusion, insecurity, unemployment, economic inequality, lack of housing and traffic and these problems reduce the quality of urban life strongly. Nevertheless, policy-makers and planners at national and international level emphasize on the ability of cities to improve the quality of human life (Rezvani and et al, 2009: 2). Cities, as the context of human biology have a fundamental role in creating consent and in fact, it is the former of the style of life and determines the quality of his life. Attentions to the quality of the human environment not only encourage the human to be in it but it will be effective in making a sense of satisfaction in human (Smith and levermore, 2008: 5). So, a concept entitled the quality of life has been propounded and studied in order to solve human problems and improve urban quality of life. The concept of the quality of life shows general characteristics of the environment in a region which can be a used as a powerful tool to monitor community development planning. It has also been defined as a scale to measure the degree of meeting of the psychological and material needs of the community and family (Pal, 2005: 24).

The quality of life has attracted attention in recent years and it has increasingly been the subject of scientific research and theory in different areas and systems. The study of this concept is based on the underlying assumption that the social and physical environment can affect the happiness and welfare of people in one place (Limber, 2006: 2). Generally, the approach of the quality of urban life is an attempt to create a healthy city and to provide municipal services appropriate and accessible to everyone in the framework of sustainability and create a feeling of satisfaction (Harpham et al, 2001: 109).

The concept of the of quality of life is assumed as the overall reflects of personal feeling of health includes all the factors involved in human satisfaction and to a large extent is affected by the social, economic and environmental quality of city (Poll, Van, 1997: 2). The social health of the citizens is the key components and in another word and by the explanation of the World Health Organization, it is the most complex and controversial aspect of the index of health and it is the most important scope of the quality of life. This aspect of health is as an indicator to show the mental health of citizens and in other words it is a criterion to determine the satisfaction or dissatisfaction of individuals and social groups with the quality of life (Samii and et al, 2010: 3). With emphasis on the construction of the city and its physical form and readability, the quality of environment propounds elements such as identity, neighborhood characteristics, speech clarity and street pattern and etc as influential factors in determining the quality of life (Bahrain, 2010: 211). At the same time improving the quality of life in today's communities are the results of improving economic factors such as income distribution, access to public services, economic growth and savings, productivity and capital (Khademi, 2011: 28).

In this study, we are going to study the amount of Citizen Satisfaction with the quality of life in the old and new fabric of the city of Khash to provide the most appropriate methods for future planning by explaining the scientific ways.

The goals of the research

- 1- Measuring of citizen's satisfaction with the quality of life in the old and new fabric of the city of Khash.
- 2- Valuation and ranking the factors affecting the quality of life in the old and new fabric of the city.
3. The relationship between socioeconomic status and physical satisfaction with the quality of the environment of the living.

History of research

Perhaps the most famous of the highest quality ever taken place. The United Nations Human Development Report, the Human Development Report by the WHO in 1990 and successively developed as far as the most comprehensive studies on quality of life was raised. Quality of Life in New Zealand reported in 2007 showed a picture of life in New Zealand and was characterized by an improved quality of life, in what areas or areas where improvement is needed. This report covers 68 key indicators of quality of life. The purpose of this report was to provide information that could explain the perceived economic and environmental conditions, to describe and quantify the quality of life for residents living in urban areas in New Zealand, to be used.

Projects in the United States of America Jacksonville's quality of life, quality of life as "a feeling of well-being or satisfaction resulting from factors that are present in the external environment" are defined. External environment is divided into nine factors, and each factor is a target image. And indicators to measure progress toward these goals are determined. The nine factors are: economic, political / governmental, environmental, health, education, social, cultural - recreational, public safety and transport (Fattahi et al, 2011, 29-23). Since the late 1960s, the concept of quality of life in terms of social justice, social welfare, public life, quality of living environment and geographical sciences, literature and extensive research was conducted by researcher's worldwide geography. Iranian globally and multiple studies have been conducted on the quality of life in urban areas:

In the Nelson et al Study (2005), the presence or absence of hot water and other facilities index to measure the quality of urban housing is considering.

In the Harris study (1976), in this study, the connection between housing quality and the characteristics of the housing price is to be created.

In the Ha and Weber Study (1994), 1040 people through questionnaires in order to assess the current situation and living conditions of living index is based on 77 questions and answers were in terms of satisfaction. Furthermore, given the importance of ideal and actual situations presented.

In the Carp and et al study (1976), Evaluation of a rapid transit system in coastal area residents was conducted on the environmental quality of life. This study evaluated the audience about their current living situation based on more than 100 properties in question were settled.

In the Bonaiuto and et al study (2003), as indicators of environmental quality perception of residence and neighborhood associations in urban areas, two instruments measuring quality connection with the residents live in urban environments is presented. These tools include the 11 criteria that perception of the environment in urban residential environment measures and criteria to measure the dependence of a neighborhood has been applied.

Moloudi (2010), the criteria and sub-criteria indicate that the consent of any of the physical characteristics of spatial structure - there is no content and performance at low quality of the new city Hashtgerd is many reasons.

Rezvani et al (2010), Quality of life domains were identified as follows: housing, water, light, food, fuel for cooking and heating, collection and disposal of garbage and sewage networks, health, safety, employment, ownership of the goods durable, education, information and communication, participation, freedom, fun and leisure.

Kokabee (2008), indicators and measures of quality of urban life in multiple dimensions and studies worldwide have examined.

The scope of the studying region

The city of Khash is one of the cities of Sistan-Baluchestan province of Iran and is located in the South East of Iran and its distance to the center of the province (Zahedan) is 175 km. This city is located at eastern longitude of 60 degrees, 55 minutes and 61 degrees 30 minutes and at northern latitude of 27 degrees 50 minutes and 28 degrees 40 minutes and it is located in a smooth plain directed from the north-west to south-east and the mountains of Panjangosht are located in the west of the city and the heights of Dahana, the valley of Amr, Zirok are located in the East and Northeast of the city. The peak of Taftan is located near the city in northern part of the city. This city has 2 urban centers, 3 counties, 11 districts, 799 villages and it includes 4 area and 14 regions.

Figure (1): the area under study, Source: search results

Discussion and conclusion

The analysis of citizens' satisfaction with the quality of the environment of living in old and new fabric

The one-sample T-test is used for getting the amount of citizens' satisfaction from the quality of living environment and chosen criteria from the citizens' prospective. The results of T-test show whether it can be generalized to the entire population.

Considering that the range of 5 option of Likert scale was used in questionnaire and the ranks from 1 to 5 are dedicated to the answers and the score of 1 indicates a very low degree of satisfaction and 5 representing the highest level of satisfaction, therefore the number of 3 is chosen as the commentary medium of the answers so, the average score of the amount of satisfaction has been compared by the number 3.

Table (1): Rate each of the sixteen constituent environmental quality criterion

Old fabric	New fabric	Indicators
3.55	3.65	Sound
3.62	3.45	Odor
3.30	3.22	Pollution
3.10	3.26	rubbish
3.20	3.52	Security
2.62	3.02	crowd
2.24	2.14	Urban facilities
2.20	2.38	Place to belong
2.0	2.46	Buildings
2.55	2.51	Network Access
2.24	2.11	Green spaces
2.30	2.4	Social relations
2.66	2.3	Access to Services
2.33	2.25	Vitality
3.20	3.02	Readability
2.00	2.33	discipline

Source: search results

As it can be seen, among the sixteen constituent elements of environmental quality in the new fabric, seven factors (noise, and pollution, rubbish, safety, congestion and readability) have obtained a score greater than 3 and 9 factors have obtained a score lower than three. In old fabric, the six factors (Noise, and pollution, rubbish, safety and readability) have obtained a score greater than 3 and the rest are below average. It can be seen that the factors which have obtained the high and low ranks of the three average limits are similar in two fabrics except in one factor.

Table (2): T test scores obtained from the breakdown fabric old and new

Old fabric		New fabric	
Less than 3	More than 3	Less than 3	More than 3
Urban facilities	Sound	Urban facilities	Sound
Place to belong	Odor	Place to belong	Odor
Buildings	Pollution	Buildings	Pollution
Network Access	rubbish	Network Access	rubbish
Green spaces	Security	Green spaces	Security
Social relations	Readability	Social relations	Readability
Access to Services		Access to Services	crowd
Vitality		Vitality	
discipline		discipline	
crowd			

Source: search results

If we compute the average of the sixteen benchmarks or criteria together in both the scope of the study, the number of 2/81 for new fabric and the number of 2/76 for old fabric will be obtained, namely the numbers less than the average number of 3. They are very close to each others.

The amount of Satisfaction from home, neighborhood and city in new and old fabric: In a separate table, by considering all aspects it was asked from the respondents to express the amount of their satisfaction from the situation of living at home, their neighborhood and city. This issue has been shown by using of T-test and by the frequencies of the responses.

Table (3): Satisfaction of the house, neighborhoods and city the fabric new and old

Old fabric	New fabric	Indicator
2.17	2.95	Satisfaction of the House
2.05	2.47	Satisfaction with the neighborhoods
2.44	2.56	Satisfaction of the City

Source: search results

Valuation and ranking of the factors affecting the quality of the environment of living

A. old fabric

The results of ranking of effective factors on the quality of environment in old fabric have been presented in table (4). As it can be seen, the items of place belonging and readability have the highest impact and the factors of social relations, buildings and green space have the least amount of impact on the quality of the environment in the Old fabric.

Table (4): Ranking Factors affecting environmental quality in Old fabric

The impact percent each of the Indicators	Coefficient β	Indicators	Rank
11.20	0.219	Place to belong	1
12.00	0.190	Odor	2
8.10	0.111	Readability	3
7.12	0.114	Pollution	4
7.10	0.123	discipline	5
6.85	0.119	crowd	6
6.06	0.102	Security	7
5.66	0.088	Vitality	8
5.10	0.084	Access to Services	9
5.09	0.081	Network Access	10
5.15	0.087	rubbish	11
4.23	0.072	Sound	12
4.10	0.059	Urban facilities	13
3.88	0.059	Social relations	14
3.82	0.054	Buildings	15
3.79	0.051	Green spaces	16

Source: search results

B. New fabric

The values of β must be used for finding out the importance and role of the independent variables in predicting of regression equation. Since the amounts of Beta are standardized thus we can judge the relative importance of variables through it. The large amount of beta indicates the relative importance and its role in predicting the dependent variable. It should be noted that the coefficient B are used to predict changes while the beta β coefficient is used for the amount of the effect of independent variables on the dependent variable. The results of ranking of sixteen factors in new fabric have been presented in table (5). As it can be seen, the items of rubbish, social relations and security have the highest degree of effectiveness and the items of Pollution, green space and sound have the lowest degree of effectiveness on the quality of environment in new fabric.

Table (5): Ranking Factors affecting the quality of new fabric

The impact percent each of the Indicators	Coefficient β	Indicators	Rank
8.89	0.170	rubbish	1
7.68	0.136	Social relations	2
7.17	0.135	Security	3
7.67	0.134	Place to belong	4
7.49	0.139	Access to Services	5
6.69	0.121	discipline	6
6.27	0.120	Readability	7
6.08	0.110	crowd	8
5.45	0.099	Odor	9
5.27	0.101	Buildings	10
5.21	0.089	Network Access	11
5.23	0.088	Vitality	12
5.21	0.085	Urban facilities	13
5.08	0.094	Pollution	14
4.82	0.092	Green spaces	15
4.29	0.080	Sound	16

Source: search results

The Comparison of the results of the two models

As it can be seen in table (6) significant differences can be seen in the ranking of the items of two models. Three factors which have the most importance in new fabric are: accessing to services, social relationships and rubbish while the three factors which have the most importance in old fabric are: place belonging, network access and crowd.

Table (6): Ranking the indicators the two models

The influence percent the model indicators (Old fabric)	Two model indicators	The influence percent the model indicators (New fabric)	One model indicators	Rank
12.20	Place to belong	7.99	Access to Services	1
12.00	Network Access	7.55	Social relations	2
7.30	crowd	7.87	rubbish	3
7.29	Pollution	7.59	Urban facilities	4
7.11	Vitality	7.56	Buildings	5
6.85	Readability	6.80	Network Access	6
6.10	Security	6.41	Vitality	7
5.69	discipline	6.19	Security	8
5.23	Sound	5.49	Place to belong	9
5.13	Buildings	5.41	crowd	10
5.11	Urban facilities	5.30	Readability	11
4.35	Access to Services	5.20	Green spaces	12
4.02	Odor	5.10	Sound	13
3.82	Green spaces	5.03	discipline	14
3.80	rubbish	4.80	Odor	15
3.79	Social relations	4.24	Pollution	16

Source: search results

The comparison of dimension ranking of environment quality in old and new fabric

The comparison of the results shows that among the dimensions of the environment quality in new fabric, the socioeconomic dimension has had the highest impact on citizens' satisfaction from the quality of their environment of living and after them, the perceived dimension, the made dimension and the environmental dimension have had the highest impact respectively. The perceived dimension and then the environmental dimension have had the highest impact in old fabric.

Table (7): the sum of the mean score for each of the four dimensions of the environment the texture new and old

Old fabric		New fabric		Dimensions of Environmental Quality
Average Scores	Gather Scores	Average Scores	Gather Scores	
4.56	21.96	7.01	25.69	Socio-economic
4.51	13.33	5.08	19.10	The built environment
8.1	31.4	5.50	25.02	Perceived environment
6.3	33.10	5.11	27.71	Environmental

Source: search results

Table (8): rank of each of the four dimensions of the environment in the texture of the Old and New

Old fabric	New fabric	Dimensions of Environmental Quality
3	1	Socio-economic
4	3	The built environment
1	2	Perceived environment
2	4	Environmental

Source: search results

Conclusion

The quality of urban environment has been one of the new challenges of planning and management institutions in recent years. Responding to the residential and service needs, especially in cities located in the border provinces has caused that this important and affecting issue is considered less in the quality of urban life. Due to features such as lack of physical space according to the needs of society and the lack of services and facilities and its non-uniform distribution, lack of social security, it seems that Border towns have suffered serious injury in this field.

The results of investigations show that Constituent elements of environmental quality in both studied scopes, although with slight differences are identical. It was also found that although citizens' satisfaction with the quality of the environment isn't desirable but the residents of new fabric are more satisfied than the residents of old fabric. The studying of the amount of satisfaction is facing to the constituent factors of the quality of life in regions. The socio-economic dimension has the greatest influence on the citizens' satisfaction in new fabric and the citizens of the old fabric are more satisfied with perceived dimension.

Generally in new fabric, more attention should be paid by agenda planners to improve the constituent elements of environmental quality, especially in the field of urban facilities, place belonging, buildings, network access, landscaping, community relations, access to services, vitality until the relative satisfaction of these factors will be obtained and also we should be aware of other

factors that are favorable condition. In addition to the aforementioned issues about the old fabric, the factors of crowding should be considered until the improving of constituent factors of the environment quality leads to relative satisfaction with the quality of life environment of citizens.

References

1. Bahrini, S, H, (2011), Urban design process, Tehran University Press, Fifth Edition.
2. Bonaiuto, M, and et al, (2004), Neighborhood Evaluation within a Multi place perspective on Urban Activities, Environment and Behavior, Vol.36, No. 1, pp. 41-69.
3. Carp, FM., Zawadski, R.T. Shokrkon, H, (1976), Dimensions of urban environmental quality; Environment and Behavior, Vol. 8, No. 2, pp: 239-264 .
4. Fattahi, A. Khorasani, M.A. Paydar, A, (2013), Quality of Life and Human Development, Tehran, Entekhab publications.
5. Ha, M and Weber, M. J., (1994), Residential Quality and Satisfaction: Toward Developing, Residential Quality Indexes, Home Economics Research Journal, 22 (3), 296-308.
6. Harpham.T & et al, (2001), Healthy city project in developing countries:The first evaluation, south bank university,London.
7. Kademi, A.H. (2012), Assessment of urban green space and location using GIS (Case Study: Amol), MA thesis, Islamic Azad University Noor.
8. Kokabee, A, (2008), Measures of quality of urban life in urban centers, Journal of Hoviateshahr Number 1 / Fall-Winter 86.
9. Lambiri, D, (2006), Quality of life in the Economic and urban Economic Literature, JEL classification: R00, 131, R12.
10. Moloudi, J, (2010), master's thesis, geography and urban planning, urban environmental quality evaluation in the case of new cities: New City Hashtgerd, supervisor M. Rafieian, Tarbiat Modarres University.
11. Nelson, B, Jasvinder, A, Howard, A,nKristin L, (2005), Health-related quality of life predicts future health care utilization and mortality in veterans with self-reported physician-diagnosed arthritis: The veterans arthritis quality of life study Original Research Article Seminars in Arthritis and Rheumatism, Volume 34, Issue 5, Pages 755-765.
12. Pal, A.K, Kumar, U.C, (2005), Quality of life concept for the evaluation of societal development of rural community in west bangal, India, Rural Development, vol. xv,no2
13. Rezvani, M. Mitkan, A.A. Mansorian, H. Sattari. M.H, (2010), Development of indicators to measure the quality of urban life in the city Nurabad, Journal Urban - Regional Studies and Research, the first year, second edition.
14. Samiei, M, Rafiey, H, Amini, M, Akbarian, M, (2011), Iranian public health, Social Problems, First Year
15. Smith, C., Levermore,G.,(2008), Designing urban spaces and building to improve sustainability and quality of life in a warmer word, Social Indicators Research 40.
16. Van poll, Ric (1997).The perceived Quality of urban Environment A multi- attribute evaluation , university of Groningen